

Table 2. Evidence Mapping of Key Barrier Themes

Barrier Theme (Domain)	Description	Supporting Studies (Country)
1. Insufficient Professional Expertise (P)	Gaps in foundational and CTAS-specific knowledge, particularly among novice nurses, leading to high rates of under- or over-triage.	Bijani & Khaleghi, 2019 [14] (Iran); Duko et al., 2019 [15] (Ethiopia); Al-Thobaity et al., 2024 [21] (Saudi Arabia)
2. Nurse Shortages & High Workloads (S)	Chronic understaffing leading to rushed assessments, burnout, and limited capacity to engage in training.	Rosenberg, 2019 [17] (USA); Li et al., 2018 [12] (China)
3. Environmental Stressors (E)	Chaotic ED conditions (noise, interruptions, overcrowding) that impair cognitive function and decision-making.	Delmas et al., 2020 [18] (France); Bijani & Khaleghi, 2019 [14] (Iran)
4. Lack of Standardized Education (S)	High variability in triage training curricula, duration, and quality, leading to inconsistent competency levels.	Hardy & Calleja, 2018 [13] (Australia); Salifu et al., 2022 [19] (Ghana); Ouellet et al., 2025 [22] (Canada)
5. Inadequate Resources & Infrastructure (S)	Absence of dedicated training resources, such as simulation labs or updated technology, to support practical education.	Salifu et al., 2022 [19] (Ghana)
6. Cultural & Communication Barriers (P/S)	Challenges in cross-cultural communication and varying patient perceptions of urgency, especially in diverse populations.	Al-Thobaity et al., 2024 [21] (Saudi Arabia)
7. Lack of Interprofessional Collaboration (S)	Role ambiguity and poor communication between ED nurses, prehospital providers, and other hospital teams.	Reay et al., 2019 [16] (Canada)

8. Misaligned Prehospital-ED Systems (S)	Inconsistencies in triage protocols and information handover between emergency medical services and the ED.	Reay et al., 2019 [16] (Canada)
9. Insufficient Leadership & Policy Support (S)	Absence of institutional prioritization, funding, or formal policies to mandate and sustain triage education programs.	Hardy & Calleja, 2018 [13] (Australia); Salifu et al., 2022 [19] (Ghana)
10. Resistance to Change (P)	Reluctance among staff to adopt new triage protocols or educational methods due to entrenched traditional practices.	Soola et al., 2022 [20] (Iran); Taheri et al., 2015 [11] (Iran)

P=Professional, E=Environmental, S=Systemic